

Factors associated with adolescent pregnancy: A literature review

Aliza Tri Puspitasari and Nabella Indra Putry Sukmawaty*

Midwifery Study Program, Faculty of Medicine, Airlangga University, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 20(03), 1734–1737

Publication history: Received on 21 October 2023; revised on 21 December 2023; accepted on 23 December 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.20.3.2650>

Abstract

The number of high-risk pregnant women always shows a fairly large number every year. Adolescence pregnancy is in the spotlight in various countries because of the harmful effects. The purpose of this study was to determine the factors associated with adolescence pregnancy. This research uses the literature review method. The data were sourced from national scientific journal articles obtained through Google Scholar, and Pubmed using the keywords "Adolescent pregnancy", " Knowledge", "Parents", "Education" and " Economic condition". This study shows that the factors associated with adolescent pregnancy are the role of parents, latest education, sex knowledge and economic conditions.

Keywords: Adolescent pregnancy; Knowledge; Parents; Education; Economic condition.

1. Introduction

The number of high-risk pregnant women always shows a fairly large number every year. One of the risk factors is pregnant women with age less than 20 years old or teenage pregnancy [1]. Adolescence is a dynamic phase of growth and development dynamic phase in an individual's life. Adolescence progresses through 3 stages namely early adolescence (10-14 years), (15-16 years), and late adolescence (17-20 years) [2]. In adolescents, reproductive organs begin to function and secondary sexual signs grow, making it easy for sexual activity (especially among adolescents) to continue with sex. In addition, curiosity about sexual problems in adolescents is very important in the formation of the adolescents is very important in the formation of a new, more mature relationship with the opposite sex [3]. Among adolescents, sex is a problem that causing unrest in the community. There are allegations that there is a tendency of adolescence sex increasing not only in big cities, but also in small towns. In the 2017 SDKI data it was recorded that as many as 80% of women and 84% men claimed to have dated [4]. Adolescence pregnancy is in the spotlight in various countries because of the harmful effects. Various aspects are affected by adolescence pregnancy aspects, including health, education and economy. Impacts that arise from the health aspect include: risk of experiencing labor pre-term labor, the baby who is born has low birth weight (LBW), have a higher risk of death. In addition, teenagers who experience pregnancy usually do not complete education, have low economic level, and the risk to have offspring with health health and growth problems child development higher risk of neonatal mortality, increased risk of postpartum depression depression in mothers and low maternal initiation to breastfeed her baby [5]. Data according to the World Health Organization (WHO) 2017 adolescence pregnancy that occurs at the age of 15-19 years shows an average rate of 49 per 1000 adolescents in the world [6]. With this, the researcher is interested in conducting a literature study with the title "Factors associated with adolescent pregnancy".

2. Material and methods

This research uses the literature review method. The data were sourced from national scientific journal articles obtained through Google Scholar, and Pubmed using the keywords "Adolescent pregnancy", " Knowledge", "Parents", "Education" and " Economic condition". The inclusion criteria for this study were titles that fit the research theme,

* Corresponding author: Nabella Indra Putry Sukmawaty.

namely factors associated with adolescent pregnancy articles published from 2019 to 2023 (the last five years). Relevant research articles were identified using the literature review method, by comparing similar articles in the research, especially those related to adolescent pregnancy.

3. Results and discussion

Based on the collected and analyzed articles, the findings are presented as follows:

Table 1 List of Articles

No.	Author	Research Title	Method	Result
1.	Ni Made Sri Widiartini et al.	Factors causing the high incidence of teenage pregnancy in sukasada puskesmas working area	Cross Sectional	Factors associated with the incidence of teenage pregnancy is the role of parents, especially in adolescents who have a history of history of adolescent pregnancy [1].
2.	Desi Pramita Sari	The correlation of analysis factors teenager's pregnancy at batam city 2019.	The phenomenological method	Most adolescents have good knowledge about teenage pregnancy adolescent pregnancy, causative factors and the impact of adolescent pregnancy [2].
3.	Ani Retni and Fahmi Lihu	Factors associated with the occurrence of unwanted pregnancy in adolescents in the western bolangitang sub-district.	Cross Sectional	In general, adolescents who experience unwanted pregnancies have less knowledge. The rape and pregnancy due to incest in a constant state of not dealing with an unwanted pregnancy in adolescents in the District of West Bolangitang [3].
4.	Anisa Putri Alifah et al.	Factors influencing adolescent pregnancy outside of marriage.	Descriptive research method and Qualitative approach	The study indicates that there are internal and external factors that influence adolescents so that they become pregnant out of wedlock [4].
5.	Amrina Nur Rohmah et al.	A Qualitative study of the causes of premarital pregnancy in adolescents.	A qualitative study	Knowledge of adolescent reproductive health, Adolescent attitudes related to premarital sexual relations, Family conditions, Influence of partners in dating, Influence of peers, Influence of living environment [5].
6.	Ni Kadek Novia Aristanti et al.	The Level Of Adolescent Knowledge To Become One Of The Factors Causing Youth Pregnancy	A literature review	A review showed that low knowledge was one of the factors causing teenage pregnancy and increased knowledge after being given health education [6].

3.1 The relationship between parental role and adolescent pregnancy

In adolescence is span of human life at the transition period. At this time is a period transition from childhood to adulthood [4]. In this transitional period, adolescents are looking for their identity so that they have a tendency to try various new things, so they have the potential to do things outside the norms that apply in Indonesia such as consuming narcotics, engaging in free sex, consuming alcohol, and consuming drugs [5]. In addition, adolescent problems related to reproductive health are adolescents with pregnancies under the age of 20 years old at 32% [2]. Based on the results of bivariable analysis between the role of parents and the incidence of teenage pregnancy, it can be seen that there is a significant relationship between the two variables. This shows that the role of parents will affect the incidence of pregnancy in adolescents. Especially in adolescents who have experienced pregnancy in adolescence [1]. Parents play a very important role in this matter and must be able to be a role model for their children, especially in adolescence where adolescents are in a period of curiosity about many things. Sex education should start at home, because home, because

sexual problems are a private matter. However many parents are less able to meet the needs of their teenage children needs of their teenage children due to lack of knowledge about it and still think that sex education is a taboo subject to talk [1].

3.2 The relationship between education level and adolescent pregnancy

Unintended pregnancy is still a problem in the world. The magnitude of the problem of unwanted pregnancy problem is reflected in the cases cases that occur on a global, regional and national scale [3]. many adolescents have engaged in premarital sex resulting in unwanted pregnancies. Pregnancy during adolescence has difficult consequences for not only the the adolescent concerned, but also for all other family members [4]. Education level is associated with adolescent pregnancy. The better one's level of education, the better the mindset that is formed, so that this good mindset will make someone more open to new things and able to receive information well so that they have the ability to thinking in behavior [2]. education is closely related to information about reproductive health that received by a person so that they can distinguish between correct health behavior and the wrong health behavior. Level higher level of education will make it easier for a person or community to absorb information and

implement it in their daily behavior and lifestyle, especially in terms of health, so that the level of education education level can shape a person's values especially in accepting new things [2].

3.3 The relationship between knowledge of sex and adolescent pregnancy

Sex knowledge referred to in this study this research is all ways of expressing and release sexual urges that come from maturity of the sexual organs, such as dating intimate, making out, until making sexual contact, but the sexual contact, but this behavior is considered not in accordance with the norms because adolescents have not have no sexual experience. The results showed that adolescents who were used as respondents already had sexual urges such as the desire to date, make out, and have sexual contact. such as the desire to date, make out and have intercourse but lack knowledge about sex that leads to positive things, this is because teenagers get sex knowledge only from media such as the internet, pornographic movies, news and the environment of environment. This condition that resulted in increased curiosity about sex but only limited to things that lead to intimate relationships. Adolescent knowledge about sex is still very lacking. This factor is coupled with misinformation obtained from the wrong sources, such as myths about sex, pornographic VCDs, pornographic sites on the internet and others that will be porn sites on the internet and others that will make children's understanding and perception of sex to be wrong. Sex education actually means sexuality education, which is a sexual education in a broad sense that includes various aspects related to sex, including biological aspects, orientation, values sociocultural and moral values and behavior [3]. Pregnancy outside of marriage is influenced by several factors which include lack of sex education or knowledge about reproductive health reproductive health, permissiveness in social environment, the negative impact of technological advances, the influence of friends and parenting. The most dominant factor that causes the occurrence of pregnancy among adolescents are lack of sex education and the influence of friends [4]. Teenage pregnancy due to lack of knowledge about reproductive health and lack of understanding of contraceptives. The attitude of adolescents who have tendency to engage in risky sexual activities increases the incidence of adolescent pregnancy [5]. Low knowledge of teenagers about adolescent pregnancy can influence adolescents to behave negatively which can lead to pregnancy in adolescents. The more adolescents who have knowledge about reproductive health, especially promiscuous sex and teenage pregnancy, the more the number of adolescent pregnancies will increase then the number of teenage pregnancies that will occur will also increase. Low knowledge about reproductive health and sexuality can lead to wrong perceptions that can lead to sexual behavior which has an impact on the incidence of pregnancy in adolescents, but if you have the correct knowledge about reproductive health and sexuality can lead a person to avoid negative behavior [6].

3.4 The relationship economic condition and adolescent pregnancy

Condition low family economic conditions are followed by low age of first marriage as well, and vice versa, the higher the economic condition of the economic conditions of the family, the higher the age of the higher the age of first marriage. This shows that family income is related to the age of age of first marriage and pregnancy, the lower the family income, the earlier head of the family marries off her daughter. Family income levels will affect the age of young marriage, this is because in families with low income then marriage their children means the release of the burden and responsibility to support their children [2].

4. Conclusion

This study shows that the factors associated with adolescent pregnancy are the role of parents, latest education, sex knowledge and economic conditions.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgements

This article did not receive assistance from the government, private companies, or non-profit organization.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Widiartini NMS, Megaputri PS, Tangkas NMKS. Faktor Penyebab Tingginya Kejadian Kehamilan Remaja di Wilayah Kerja Puskesmas Sukasada. Simposium Kesehatan Nasional. 2022;(September):290–5.
- [2] Sari DP, HANDAYANI TY, YOLANDA K. Analisis Faktor Yang Berhubungan Dengan Kehamilan Remaja Di Kota Batam Tahun 2019. Journal Midwifery. 2019;7(2):19–27.
- [3] Retni A, Lihu F. Faktor - Faktor yang Berhubungan dengan Terjadinya Kehamilan Tidak Diinginkan pada Remaja di Wilayah Kecamatan Bolangitang Barat. Jurnal Ilmu Kesehatan. 2021;2(2):1–8.
- [4] Alifah AP, Apsari NC, Taftazani BM. Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Remaja Hamil Di Luar Nikah. Jurnal Penelitian dan Pengabdian Kpd Masyarakat. 2022;2(3):529.
- [5] Nur Rohmah A, Secha Primindari R, Alifiana Rahmawati S, Dianita Irawan D, Ika Rahmawati E, Prastyoningsih A. Studi Kualitatif Penyebab Kehamilan Pranikah Pada Remaja. Jurnal Kesehatan Kusuma Husada. 2022;13(2):221–33.
- [6] Kadek N, Aristanti N, Pamungkas MA, Lisnawati K, Studi P, Program K, et al. Tingkat Pengetahuan Menjadi Salah Satu Faktor Penyebab Kehamilan Remaja The Level Of Adolescent Knowledge To Become One Of The Factors Causing Youth Pregnancy. 2020;1–11. Available at: [https://repository.stikeswiramedika.ac.id/111/1/Ni Kadek Novia Aristanti.pdf](https://repository.stikeswiramedika.ac.id/111/1/Ni%20Kadek%20Novia%20Aristanti.pdf)